

Analysis of healthcare professionals' perceptions towards individuals with disabilities: Influence of sociodemographic and professional determinants

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Abstract

Introduction: Healthcare professionals' understanding of individuals with disabilities is essential to delivering equitable, high-quality care and fostering social inclusion. This study explores healthcare professionals' perceptions of persons with disabilities (PWDs) in Rabat, Morocco, analyzing the influence of sociodemographic and professional factors and identifying key determinants shaping these perceptions.

Methods: An analytical cross-sectional study was conducted between October and December 2021. Questionnaires were distributed to 206 healthcare professionals, and responses from 92 participants were analyzed using bivariate and multivariate statistical methods.

Results: Of the respondents, 26% held negative perceptions of PWDs, while 74% reported positive perceptions. Significant associations were identified between perceptions and factors such as gender, knowledge of disability management methods, and systematic screening practices. Multivariate analysis highlighted that knowledge of disability management methods and systematic screening significantly increased the likelihood of positive perceptions.

Discussion: This study underscores the need to address knowledge and training gaps among healthcare professionals, emphasizing the importance of fostering empathy and inclusivity. By

identifying key determinants, the findings offer actionable insights to improve professional practices and advance inclusive healthcare for individuals with disabilities.

TAKE-HOME MESSAGE: Healthcare professionals play a critical role in ensuring equitable care for persons with disabilities. By addressing gaps in knowledge and perceptions, healthcare systems can promote inclusive practices that respect the rights and dignity of all individuals. This study highlights the importance of targeted education and systematic screening in shaping positive attitudes and fostering compassionate, high-quality care for persons with disabilities.

Keywords: Disability management; inclusive care; healthcare professionals' perceptions; persons with disabilities; health determinants.

INTRODUCTION

Disability is characterized by limitations in activity or social participation resulting from physical, sensory, mental, or combined impairments, compounded by personal or environmental barriers. Three principal frameworks underpin the understanding of disability: the biomedical model, which focuses on medical treatment; the environmental model, which emphasizes inclusive surroundings; and the inclusive model, which advocates for the social integration and active participation of individuals with disabilities. These frameworks collectively form the cornerstone of inclusive societies [1-5].

Globally, addressing the needs of individuals with disabilities is both a moral and practical imperative. In Morocco, the 2014 National Household Survey revealed a prevalence rate of 6.8% among the population, with one in four households including a member with a disability. The survey highlighted critical healthcare needs such as free healthcare and assistive devices (82.3%), increased care and rehabilitation centers (47.5%), and improved access and quality of healthcare services (40% and 37.8%, respectively). Severity levels ranged from mild to moderate (6.4%) to very severe (0.6%), reflecting the varied and complex challenges faced by this population [1].

To address these challenges, Morocco has implemented extensive legislative and policy measures. These include ratifying the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2009) and embedding disability rights in its 2011 Constitution. Framework laws such as No. 34/09 and No. 97-13, coupled with the 2016–2021 government plan, aim to promote healthcare access and social inclusion. Despite these efforts, significant gaps persist in realizing equitable care for persons with disabilities, underscoring the need for a robust and inclusive healthcare system [2-6].

Globally, barriers persist at all levels of healthcare for individuals with disabilities. The World Health Organization (2021) identified negative attitudes, lack of training among healthcare professionals, and inadequate data collection as key challenges contributing to healthcare inequities. Furthermore, discriminatory practices, inaccessible facilities, and financial barriers exacerbate these disparities. Countries are legally and ethically obligated to address these inequities under frameworks such as the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and the World Health Assembly's Resolution WHA74.8, which emphasize universal health coverage and the inclusion of individuals with disabilities as vital to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals [6,7].

Attitudes play a pivotal role in shaping behaviors and outcomes for individuals with disabilities. As early as 1923, Jung defined attitudes as predispositions to act based on cognitive and emotional orientations. Later, Allport expanded this definition, emphasizing that attitudes encompass beliefs, emotions, and actions. Negative attitudes, often rooted in stigma and bias, remain a significant barrier to inclusivity, limiting access to healthcare, employment, and social participation [8,9].

Ethnographic studies and systematic reviews have documented the persistence of discriminatory attitudes among healthcare professionals. For example, Pelleboer-Gunnink et al. (2019) reported that negative perceptions often stem from a lack of knowledge and interaction with individuals with disabilities. These attitudes can lead to diagnostic overshadowing, reduced quality of care, and diminished trust in healthcare systems [10-12]. Conversely, fostering positive attitudes through education and exposure to inclusive practices has been shown to reduce stigma and improve care [13,14].

Research from countries such as the United Kingdom, Ireland, and Australia highlights the global prevalence of discriminatory attitudes. In Ireland, individuals with disabilities report higher rates of discrimination than their non-disabled counterparts, while Australian surveys reveal that over 60% of respondents express impatience or neglect towards individuals with disabilities. These findings underline the urgent need for systemic interventions to promote empathy and inclusion among healthcare providers [15-18].

This study aims to investigate healthcare professionals' perceptions of individuals with disabilities in Morocco, focusing on the influence of sociodemographic and professional determinants. By identifying the factors shaping these perceptions, the research seeks to inform strategies that enhance inclusivity and respect in healthcare practices. Understanding these dynamics is critical to developing targeted interventions that improve the quality of care for individuals with disabilities and foster a more equitable healthcare environment [19].

Ultimately, this research represents an opportunity to address a persistent challenge in public health. Through evidence-based recommendations and a focus on proactive solutions, we aim to contribute to creating a healthcare system that truly values and supports individuals with disabilities, ensuring lasting positive impacts for both patients and providers.

METHODS

Study design and research strategy

This study employed an analytical cross-sectional design conducted from October to December 2021. Its primary objective was to examine the perceptions of healthcare professionals within the medical delegation of health and social protection in Rabat, Morocco, regarding individuals with disabilities. The analysis incorporated sociodemographic variables (e.g., age, gender, professional profile, seniority) and professional factors, such as knowledge of disability care structures, experiences with systematic screening for disabling conditions, and encounters during the disclosure of a disability to parents. A systematic approach ensured the study's comprehensiveness and rigor [8,9].

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The study targeted key healthcare stakeholders directly involved in the early screening and management of disabilities. Eligible participants included gynecologists, pediatricians, general practitioners, midwives, and nurses employed at primary healthcare facilities under the medical delegation. These included 23 urban health centers, one urban health center with a maternity ward, and a reproductive health reference center. Exclusion criteria applied to professionals not meeting these criteria or those unwilling to participate.

Data collection and instruments

Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire distributed to 206 healthcare professionals. The questionnaire included predominantly closed-ended questions to capture direct and measurable responses. To ensure its validity, field interviews were conducted at pilot sites to assess comprehension of terminology and the clarity of questions.

Given the constraints imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic, the questionnaire was disseminated electronically via Google Forms and distributed through WhatsApp groups targeting eligible participants. Of the 206 distributed questionnaires, 92 were completed, yielding a response rate of 44.66%. The questionnaire focused on five themes:

1. Respondent Identification: Gender, professional role, age, and years of experience.
2. Perceptions of individuals with disabilities.

3. Knowledge of disability management methods.
4. Engagement in systematic screening for disabling conditions.
5. Experiences with disability disclosure and parental reactions.

Study variables and statistical analysis

The data were subjected to descriptive and inferential statistical analyses using RStudio software. Descriptive statistics included proportions and 95% confidence intervals to estimate the distribution of characteristics within the study population [10,11].

To explore relationships between variables, the study employed the chi-squared test of independence, with Yates' continuity correction applied where appropriate, to assess associations between categorical variables [12]. For variables demonstrating significant associations, a logistic regression model was applied to identify key determinants influencing healthcare professionals' perceptions. This approach enabled the quantification of relationships using odds ratios (ORs), providing insights into the likelihood of positive perceptions based on explanatory variables such as gender, knowledge of disability management, and experience with systematic screening.

Logistic regression and model refinement

To enhance model precision and avoid overfitting, a stepwise variable selection method was employed to isolate the most significant predictors. The final model retained three variables:

1. Gender: Demonstrating statistically significant differences in perceptions.
2. Knowledge of Disability Management: Healthcare professionals with prior knowledge showed higher odds of positive perceptions (OR: 7.92).
3. Experience with Systematic Screening: Those engaged in screening practices were 33 times more likely to hold positive perceptions (OR: 33.15).

Model coefficients were calculated using the maximum likelihood method, with statistical significance determined by the Wald test ($p < 0.05$ for all retained variables). Results were tabulated to present coefficients, ORs, standard errors, and confidence intervals, ensuring clarity and transparency [13].

Ethical aspects

The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee for Biomedical Research at the Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Mohamed V University of Rabat (approval number: C64/20). Participants were informed about the study's objectives, benefits, and strict adherence to anonymity and confidentiality throughout data collection and dissemination. Participation was entirely voluntary, with informed consent obtained before inclusion in the study [14].

RESULTS

Response rate and participant characteristics

A total of 206 questionnaires were distributed to healthcare professionals meeting the inclusion criteria, with 92 responses received, yielding an overall response rate of 44.66%. The response rate among medical staff (119 individuals) was 43.69%, while paramedical staff (87 individuals) achieved a 45.97% response rate.

Of the 92 participants, 80 (86.96%) were women and 12 (13.04%) were men. The majority were aged 41–50 years (32.61%), and a significant proportion (88.04%) had over 10 years of professional experience. In terms of professional roles, 52 (56.52%) were doctors (including general practitioners and specialists), and 40 (43.48%) were nurses (Table 1).

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of healthcare professionals (N = 92).

Characteristic	N (%)	95% CI
Age group (years)		

Characteristic	N (%)	95% CI
20–30	5 (5.43%)	0.80%–10.07%
31–40	29 (31.52%)	22.03%–41.02%
41–50	30 (32.61%)	23.03%–42.19%
> 50	28 (30.43%)	21.03%–39.84%
Gender		
Women	80 (86.96%)	80.07%–93.84%
Men	12 (13.04%)	6.16%–19.93%
Professional profile		
General doctors	40 (43.48%)	33.35%–53.61%
Specialist doctors	12 (13.04%)	6.16%–19.93%
Midwives	17 (18.48%)	10.55%–26.41%
Nurses	23 (25.00%)	16.15%–33.85%
Service		
Consultation	46 (50.00%)	39.78%–60.22%
Maternity	3 (3.26%)	0.00%–6.89%
Medicine	10 (10.87%)	4.51%–17.23%
National Immunization Program	16 (17.39%)	9.65%–25.14%
Maternal/Child Health and Family Plan.	17 (18.48%)	10.55%–26.41%
Professional experience (years)		
< 5	5 (5.43%)	0.80%–10.07%
5–10	6 (6.52%)	1.48%–11.57%
> 10	81 (88.04%)	81.41%–94.67%

Perceptions towards individuals with disabilities

The study found that 24 participants (26%) held negative perceptions towards individuals with disabilities (95% CI: 17.11%–35.06%), while 68 participants (74%) exhibited positive perceptions (95% CI: 64.94%–82.89%).

Factors influencing knowledge, skills, and attitudes

1. Knowledge:

- 15 participants (16%) lacked awareness of disability types (95% CI: 8.76%–23.85%).
- Of the 77 participants (84%) who reported knowledge of disability types, 46% were familiar with fewer than four types.
- Additionally, 55 participants (60%) were unaware of methods for addressing disabilities, while 62 participants (67%) were unfamiliar with existing disability management frameworks.
- 65 participants (71%) lacked awareness of the rights of individuals with disabilities.

2. Skills (Know-How):

- Among 45 participants (49%) who routinely followed up with newborns, 22 (49%) did not screen for disabling conditions systematically.
- Of the 23 participants (25%) who screened newborns, only 5 (22%) ensured screening was comprehensive.
- Despite these gaps, 35 participants (38%) reported receiving basic training in systematic screening, while 81 participants (88%) had never received training in medical or social disability management.

3. *Attitudes:*

- Of the 42 participants (46%) who had experience disclosing a disability, 93% found it challenging. Among these:
 - 43% reported parental refusal to accept the diagnosis.
 - 10% encountered parental aggression.
 - 48% observed acceptance of the diagnosis.

Associations between perceptions and key variables

Statistical analysis revealed significant associations between healthcare professionals’ perceptions and the following factors (Table 2):

- *Gender:* Women demonstrated significantly more positive perceptions ($p = 0.002$).
- *Knowledge of disability management:* Participants with knowledge were more likely to have positive perceptions ($p = 0.0126$).
- *Systematic screening practices:* Professionals with screening experience were notably more positive ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2. Summary of dependency tests between perceptions and various factors.

Variable	X-squared	df	p-value
Profile	2.7504	3	0.4317
Gender	9.4896	1	0.0021
Age Group	11.829	3	0.0080
Professional Seniority	9.1989	2	0.0101
Knowledge of Disability Management	6.2239	1	0.0126
Systematic Screening	11.794	1	0.0006
Experience with Disability Disclosure	11.044	2	0.0040
Parental Reactions	26.809	3	<0.001

Logistic regression model

The regression analysis identified three key predictors:

- *Gender:* Male participants were less likely to hold positive perceptions (OR = 0.11; $p = 0.013$).
- *Knowledge of disability management:* Knowledge increased the likelihood of positive perceptions (OR = 7.92; $p = 0.015$).
- *Systematic screening experience:* Screening experience was the strongest predictor of positive perceptions (OR = 33.15; $p < 0.001$).

Table 3. Logistic regression results for factors influencing perceptions.

Variable	Estimate	Odds Ratio	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
Intercept	-2.7250	0.0660	0.9658	-2.821	0.0048
Male Gender	-2.1974	0.1105	0.8832	-2.488	0.0128
Knowledge of Disability Management	2.0683	7.9182	0.8534	2.424	0.0154
Systematic Screening Experience	4.0057	33.1526	0.8945	4.478	<0.001

DISCUSSION

This study revealed significant associations between healthcare professionals' perceptions of Persons With Disabilities (PWDs) and key variables, such as gender, knowledge of disability management methods, and systematic screening practices. These findings align with existing literature, underscoring the importance of sociodemographic and professional factors in shaping attitudes and behaviors in healthcare settings.

Gender and empathy in healthcare

The study demonstrated that male healthcare professionals are less likely to have positive perceptions of PWDs than their female counterparts (OR = 0.11). This finding aligns with previous research indicating that women exhibit greater empathy and emotional recognition, a critical component in providing compassionate care [15,16].

Studies on Theory of Mind have consistently shown that women excel in interpreting mental states and recognizing subtle emotional cues, particularly in caregiving roles [17,18]. These gender differences may reflect evolutionary pressures favoring female proficiency in caregiving and emotional attunement [16]. Empathy plays a pivotal role in healthcare, influencing not only patient satisfaction but also the quality of care delivered. Enhancing empathy among male professionals through targeted training may improve their perceptions of PWDs and foster more inclusive practices [17].

Knowledge and perception of disability management

Healthcare professionals with knowledge of disability management methods were approximately 7.9 times more likely to have positive perceptions of PWDs (OR = 7.92). However, the study also highlighted significant gaps in this area, with 60% of participants lacking awareness of disability management frameworks. These deficiencies can negatively affect the quality of care provided to PWDs and their families, as seen in other studies [19]. For example, in French Guiana, parents of children with autism spectrum disorders reported improved adaptation strategies and reduced distress when healthcare professionals effectively transferred knowledge about disability management [20].

Enhancing healthcare professionals' understanding of disability rights, frameworks, and management techniques could mitigate barriers to care and improve patient outcomes. These findings reinforce the need for structured education and training programs to bridge these knowledge gaps.

Systematic screening and early detection

The study found that systematic screening for disabling conditions was strongly associated with positive perceptions of PWDs (OR = 33.15). Despite this, nearly 49% of healthcare professionals did not routinely screen for disabling conditions, citing insufficient training and unfavorable professional contexts. These findings mirror global trends showing disparities in preventive care and early detection for PWDs [21,22].

Systematic screening is critical in reducing healthcare disparities. For instance, research indicates that women with intellectual disabilities are less likely to participate in cancer screenings unless adequately supported [23,24]. Improved training and support systems can empower healthcare professionals to incorporate routine screening practices, thereby addressing health inequities among PWDs.

Impact of attitudes on healthcare delivery

Negative perceptions among healthcare professionals create significant barriers to healthcare access for PWDs. Previous studies have demonstrated that unfavorable attitudes can lead to delays in diagnosis, reduced patient engagement, and suboptimal care [25,26].

Conversely, fostering positive attitudes can enhance trust, communication, and patient outcomes, promoting an inclusive healthcare environment [27].

Policy implications and Morocco's commitment

Morocco has made commendable strides in supporting PWDs through legislative measures, such as framework law n° 34/09 and the national action plan 2015–2021, which emphasize inclusivity and access to healthcare. However, gaps remain in the implementation and coordination of these policies [28]. Strengthening education and training initiatives within the healthcare system is essential to bridge these gaps and translate policy into practice.

Study limitations

The study's limitations include its relatively small sample size and focus on a single geographical area, which may limit the generalizability of findings. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported data introduces the possibility of bias, such as social desirability or confirmation bias. Future research should expand the scope to include private and university hospitals and explore interventions to address the identified gaps.

CONCLUSION

This study provides valuable insights into the perceptions of healthcare professionals towards Persons With Disabilities within the medical delegation of Rabat, Morocco. Significant associations were identified between positive perceptions and key variables, including gender, knowledge of disability management methods, and systematic screening practices. These findings underscore the critical role of education, training, and systematic approaches in fostering inclusive healthcare environments.

Despite Morocco's strong legislative framework supporting PWDs, gaps persist in healthcare professionals' knowledge, skills, and attitudes, as well as in the early detection of disabling conditions. Addressing these deficiencies through targeted interventions, such as enhanced training programs and awareness campaigns, is essential. A healthcare system that prioritizes empathy, inclusivity, and accessibility can significantly improve the quality of life for PWDs and their families.

Promoting a positive perception among healthcare professionals is not merely an ethical imperative but a practical strategy to overcome barriers, ensure equitable healthcare access, and align with global commitments, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Future efforts should focus on expanding research, improving training, and fostering collaboration across all levels of the healthcare system to build a more inclusive and compassionate society.

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